

A meadow grasshopper *Conocephalus longipennis* (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae) predator of rice yellow stem borer egg masses

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Experiments to determine the egg parasitization incidence of YSB by taping egg masses to plants in the field revealed a high level of predation by an unknown insect. Suspected predators were collected and caged with potted rice plants laden with stem borer egg masses. Adults of a meadow grasshopper or katydid, *Conocephalus longipennis* (Haan), produced identical predation symptoms as those found in the field. Subsequent field trials using marked egg masses showed predation ranged from 17 to 65% over the sampling dates, with an overall average of 46% (see table).

Rate of predation of <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> egg masses		
by <i>Conocephalus longipennis</i>, IRRI Farm, 1980-81. ^{a/}		
Date egg masses were exposed	Egg masses exposed (no.)	Predation (%)
6 Nov 80	24	17
28 Nov 80	32	25
7 Jan 81	72	65
14 Jan 81	24	45
17 Sep 81	28	46
28 Sep 81	40	60
9 Oct 81	52	65
^{a/} Egg masses were found and marked in the field and the sites revisited to note predation		